

Integrated pest management—insects

Parasitization of *Tagosodes orizicolus* and *T. cubanus* in northeastern Colombian ricefields

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Biological control of pests in integrated pest management (IPM) programs requires precise information on occurrence and effectiveness of natural enemies in attacking the pests. We studied *T. orizicolus* and *T. cubanus* parasitization in commercial irrigated ricefields at five locations representative of rice-growing areas of Norte de Santander Department, Colombia. On each farm, a field was selected at planting time and sampled at randomly selected sites every 7 d. A sample consisted of 40 sweeps taken in 20 sites/field. A sweep was a stroke with the net in either direction; one sweep was taken with every forward step. Samples were placed in plastic bags and brought to the laboratory for study. *Tagosodes* spp. were selected, sorted by species, and examined for evidence of parasitization by *Elenchus* sp. (Strepsiptera:Elenchidae).

Parasitization percentage for *T. orizicolus* and *T. cubanus* in ricefields. Norte de Santander, Colombia.

Analysis of weighted-least-squares estimates for probability of parasitization of *T. orizicolus* and *T. cubanus* in ricefields. Norte de Santander, Colombia.

Parameter	Estimate	Estimated SE	χ^2	P
Intercept	0.2500	0.0086	851.62	0.0001
Plant age	0.0018	0.0003	31.60	0.0001
Species	0.0198	0.0086	5.32	0.0211
Plant age × species	0.0018	0.0003	31.32	0.0001

Data were subjected to analysis of variance. Percent parasitization was calculated for each species. We used a linear model for repeated measurement analysis (PROC CATMOD, SAS) to calculate the probability of parasitization for each species and plant age.

Significant differences in parasitization at each plant age and for species were found (see table). Plant age × species interaction was significant, indicating each species responds differently to parasitoid attacks and percentage of

parasitism depends on plant age. The probability of parasitization (PP) was estimated as

$$T. orizicolus \text{ PP} = (0.00190) (\text{plant age})$$

$$T. cubanus \text{ PP} = (-0.00180) (\text{plant age})$$

PP for *T. orizicolus* increases with plant age while that for *T. cubanus* is not affected (see figure). This information will be useful to define IPM strategies for *T. orizicolus* and to help understand the effect of natural enemies in controlling *T. orizicolus* populations. ■

Hydrellia wirthi Korytkowski: a new rice pest in Colombia

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In Valle del Cauca Department, Colombia, *Hydrellia griseola* (F.) is a sporadic rice pest. Farmers usually apply carbofuran at planting to prevent seedling damage. A pyrethroid combined with a herbicide is applied later. In spite of this frequent insecticide use, little is known about the pest's biology in Colombia.

Hydrellia larvae and pupae were collected in the field. Individual pupae were placed on a petri dish in the laboratory. As adults emerged, they were placed in alcohol. Samples of larvae, pupae, and adults were identified at IRRI as *Hydrellia wirthi* Korytkowski. This is the first report of the pest in rice in Colombia. *H. griseola* was not recovered in the study.

Whether *H. wirthi* causes damage and affects yield as *H. griseola* does is not known. Action thresholds for use in integrated pest management in Colombia need to be reviewed for *H. griseola* and established for *H. wirthi*. ■

Colombian ricefield spiders

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Little is known about the role of spiders in controlling insect pests of rice in Latin America.

Reports have been conflicting on number and taxonomic identity of spider species in Colombian ricefields. This study aimed to identify the spider specimens in commercial irrigated ricefields in Valle del Cauca Department, Colombia. Spiders were collected with a standard sweep net, although some species were collected with an aspirator. Sampling started 5 d after panicle emergence; fields were sampled weekly

Spiders from irrigated ricefields. Valle del Cauca Department, Colombia, 1990-91.

Taxon	Locality
Anyphaenidae	
<i>Anyphaena</i> (near) <i>affinis</i>	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Araneidae	
<i>Alpaida trispinosa</i> (Keyserling)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Alpaida veniliae</i> (Keyserling)	Paso de la Torre
<i>Argiope argentata</i> (F.)	Caloto, Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsk.)	Palmira, Ginebra, Paso de la Torre
<i>Cyclosa walckenaeri</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Eriophora</i> sp.	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Eustala fuscovittata</i> (Keyserling)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Gasteracantha cancriformis</i> (L.)	Caloto, Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Gea heptagon</i> (Hentz)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Clubionidae	
<i>Cheiracanthium inclusum</i> (Hentz)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Linyphiidae	
<i>Centromerus</i> sp.	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Lycosidae	
<i>Pardosa near saxatilis</i> (Hentz)	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Pardosa milvina</i> (Hentz)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Oxyopidae	
<i>Oxyopes salticus</i> (Hentz)	Caloto, Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Tetragnathidae	
<i>Tetragnatha straminea</i> Emerton	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	Palmira, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Metidae	
<i>Leucauge argyra</i> (Walkenaer)	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Leucauge</i> sp.	Jamundí
Theridiidae	
<i>Chryso pulcherrima</i> (Mello-Leitao)	Palmira, Paso de la Torre
<i>Theridula gonygaster</i> Simon	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Thomisidae	
<i>Misumenops pallida</i> Keyserling	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Misumenoides paucispinosus</i> Keyserling	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Synaemops rubropunctatum</i> Mello-Leitao	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Salticidae	
<i>Paraphidippus</i> sp.	Palmira, Jamundí
<i>Phidippus clarus</i> Keyserling	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre

until harvest. Experts in Brazil, USA, and the Philippines identified them.

Twenty-seven species belonging to 23 genera and 11 families were identified (see table). The most abundant families in descending order were Tetragnathidae,

Salticidae, and Lycosidae. Araneidae was the family with the most species (10) from eight genera. Studies are underway to determine the importance of these species in controlling rice pests. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Ground golden snail *Ampullarius (Pomacea) canaliculata* as fertilizer increases rice yield

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Golden snails are abundant in the Philippines, causing much damage to lowland rice plants. Golden snails must be picked and placed on roads or in areas without water to eliminate them from ricefields.

Masses of golden snail were gathered, crushed, and sun-dried for 3-4 d. Crushed snails were then hammer-milled and basally applied as organic fertilizer to direct seeded IR74 at 0, 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 t/ha during wet (WS) and dry seasons (DS) on a clay loam soil in lower Paatan, Kabacan, Cotabato, Philippines. Results were significant. An increase in yield of about 50% at 0.75 t/ha equivalent application rate over the control was attributed to the ground snail fertilizer, which has 94.78% dry matter, 16.49% crude protein, and 2.54% ether extract.

The procedure eradicates the pest and increases rice yield. ■

Effect of different levels of ground golden snail on yield of irrigated rice.^a

Application rate (t/ha)	Mean yield (t/ha)	
	WS	DS
0.25	3.7 a	4.8 b
0.50	4.9 b	5.0 b
0.75	5.4 c	5.3 c
Control	3.6 a	3.8 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Four replications.